

Iron Age Cultic Place at Lachish

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Excavations at Tell ed-Duweir (ancient Lachish) in 1966 and 1968 directed by Y. Aharoni uncovered what the excavator understood as an Iron Age cultic place in the northeastern part of the site, comprised of what he referred to as a 'Sanctuary' and a nearby 'High Place'. These were located very close to a much later cultic place, the so-called 'Solar Shrine', a temple belonging to the later Persian-Hellenistic period occupation of Lachish. The excavator associated the construction of these Iron Age features with stratum V of the site, and argued that the Sanctuary had been destroyed and gone out of use also in stratum V, dating to the latter part of the tenth century BCE (the earlier part of the local Iron Age IIA), while the High Place had continued until Level III (the local Iron Age IIB), which was destroyed in 701 BCE during an Assyrian campaign against the kingdom of Judah (to which Lachish belonged). The Sanctuary is a simple, rectangular one-room structure of about 3.3m x 2.3m, with a plastered floor, stone-built benches, a stone-built raised podium in one corner. The contents of the room include: a small limestone altar with four roughly formed 'horns' at the corners; three cylindrical ceramic stands, as well as two special bowls with protruding peg-shaped bases that fit the bowl into the upper opening of two of those stands; several ceramic chalices and lamps; and several completely or partially preserved regular domestic vessels, including bowls, kraters, cooking pots, and jugs. A small stone interpreted by the excavator as a cultic standing stone is more likely for grinding. The publication of the Sanctuary leaves several questions about its stratigraphy open, and it may have more than one phase of construction. Based on more recent excavations in this part of the site and current knowledge of the local Iron Age IIA ceramic sequence, its construction and use only in stratum V appears to be correct, though some vessel forms could place it slightly earlier (near the beginning of the tenth century BCE) than other remains from this stratum. The form of the building and its contents continue a tradition of cultic rooms already well known in the southern Levant during the Bronze Age. The excavator understood the rear wall of the Sanctuary as continuing beyond that building and further to the southeast, where it connected to two terrace walls that formed a raised area, the High Place. Nearby, but not between these terrace walls, was found an upright standing stone, the remains of a burnt tree or wooden pole that the excavator interpreted as cultic as well, and a favissa pit with a few small, chiseled stones that the excavator also interpreted as standing stones that had now been disposed of. The excavator dated these features to different Iron Age strata, between V and III. The limited expose of the High Place in excavation, as well as the rather limited stratigraphic detail in the excavator's final report, make his stratigraphic interpretation difficult rather tentative. The architectural connection to the Sanctuary is especially uncertain. The remains found point to some sort of cultic activity in this area, but not clearly as a single High Place as per the excavator.

Date Range: 950 BCE - 701 BCE

Region: Approximate location of the Iron Age cultic place at Lachish

Region tags: Canaan

This is the approximate location of the Iron Age cultic place at Lachish, which is now backfilled and not visible. Immediately adjacent to the east is the so-called 'Solar Shrine' of the Persian-Hellenistic period.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Aharoni, Yohanan. 1975. Investigations at Lachish: The Sanctuary and the Residency (Lachish V). Tel Aviv: Gateway.
- Source 2: Ussishkin, David. 2004. "A Synopsis of the Stratigraphical, Chronological and Historical Issues." Pages 50-119 in The Renewed Archaeological Excavations at Lachish (1973-1994), Vol. I. Edited by David Ussishkin. Tel Aviv: Tel Aviv University.
- Source 3: Zukerman, Alexander. 2012. "A Re-Analysis of the Iron Age IIA Cult Place at Lachish." *Ancient Near Eastern Studies* 49:24-60.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

- Scientific

Years of excavation:

- Year range: 1966, 1968

Name of excavation

- Official or descriptive name: No specific name.

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Tree, grove, or forest

Notes: The burnt remains of a tree or wooden pole found with a standing stone near to the High Place was understood as cultic by the excavator, but this is not possible to verify.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Terracing

Notes: The High Place is located on what the excavator interpreted as an artificial elevation created with terrace walls, but the limited excavation there makes this hard to verify.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The stratum V occupation of Lachish now appears to have been quite robust, with a defensive wall, but note that this might be slightly later than the Shrine, based on the ceramic typology of vessels found in the latter.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As noted in the description, the stratigraphic position and relationships of the Sanctuary, High Place and their various possible phases is uncertain.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Sacrificial

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The excavator interpreted ashy material in the Sanctuary to be an indication of violent destruction, but it is unclear from available photos how much of this there was.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not possible to state whether these features were used for one deity (such as the Israelite deity YHWH) or multiple of the Canaanite deities worshiped in the region. The excavator interpreted the burnt tree and wooden pole found near the High Place as an 'Asherah', a representation of the Canaanite goddess of the same name as a tree or pole, which

is mentioned in the Hebrew Bible (e.g. Deut 16:21).

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Field doesn't know

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This depends on whether or not the High Place was really a built structure related to the Sanctuary.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

- ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials
– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:
– Field doesn't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:
– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:
– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:
– Field doesn't know

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:
– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:
– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It could be considered present if either the Israelite god YHWH or local Canaanite god Baal were worshipped/sacrificed to here.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: If there was a cultic image of a god present (as is known in Canaanite religion) but not preserved, ie made of a perishable material.

Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: Although difficult to say exactly how, as sacrifices seems to have been conducted, this would be a form of communication.

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Only a few people could fit inside the Sanctuary at any one time.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Unknown, but plausibly quite often.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
– Field doesn't know

Notes: If not intoxicants per se, the incense burned in the bowls that fit into the ceramic stands and in the chalices would have modified the smell within the Sanctuary.

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:
– Yes [specify]: This would be one function of the small altar found in the Sanctuary. Also, the bones of sheep, goat, and cattle, as well as the domestic pottery vessels found in the Sanctuary, could relate to sacrifice and cultic feasting.

↳ Are there human sacrifices:
– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Valuable offerings made of perishable materials could have been present, but unpreserved archaeologically.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The domestic vessels found in the sanctuary could have contained animal or agricultural produce offerings.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The special bowls that fit into the ceramic stands and the chalices show signs of the burning of incense within them.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The bones of sheep, goat, and cattle, as well as the domestic vessels found in the Sanctuary could be related to cultic feasting.

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is quite possible that specialist cultic personnel, that is to say "priests" as known from the Hebrew Bible and the wider ancient Near East, could have been the ones performing rituals here, but it is difficult to say if such shrines could or could not function without them; there seems to be no positive evidence that they only functioned through priests, however.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It may be that the Shrine and High Place (if the latter was really as the excavator thought) served the cultic needs of the stratum V occupation at Lachish, and that other community activities happened in and around it, but this is impossible to know.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Field doesn't know

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: This particular cultic place is not itself mentioned in any text, but three elements of it (at least as understood by the excavator) are reflected in the Hebrew Bible. Cultic standing stones (Hebrew "Masseboth") are mentioned several times in the Hebrew Bible, while the biblical Hebrew term "Bamah" is typically understood to mean a "high place", as in a natural or artificial platform for cultic practice (hence the name given by the excavator to the second element in this Iron Age cultic place). However, the exact meaning of biblical Hebrew "bamah" is uncertain from the text.

↳ Are they written at this place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they oral:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Iron Age Cultic Place at Lachish, Aharoni, Yohanan. *Investigations at Lachish: The Sanctuary and the Residency (Lachish V)*. Tel Aviv: Gateway, 1975.

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